

Husband's Flaws And The Demands Of The Objectives Of Shari'a: A Study Of The Viewpoints Of Fuqahaa

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: January 29, 2022</p> <p>Accepted: August 30, 2022</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Flaws, Husband, Shariah, Jurists, Viewpoints, School Of Thought</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7810972</p>	<p><i>Islam is the religion of leniency and ease which asserts to take all measures to save its followers from hardships and troubles. Since Islam teaches haleness and safety, therefore forbids fraud in trade and selling defective things. But if this flaw relates to the husband then the wife can be granted the right to repeal the Nikah as per the demands of the objectives of Shari'a. The reason for it is the fact that husband can have four Nikah at a time in islam, while the wife cannot do so. Therefore the objectives of Shari'a demand to save the wife from this trouble.</i></p> <p><i>But it's important to remember that Islam is a well-balanced religion that opposes violating anyone's rights. Because of this, the wife does not have the authority to dissolve the nikah for any flaws in her spouse; despite the fact that jurists (fuqahaa) have identified several physical, sexual, mental, and psychological flaws in the husband that allow the wife the right to dissolve the nikah. However, a complete cancellation of Nikah as a result of these flaws would be against Shari'a's principles, because the needs of the objectives of Shari'a require persistence and permanence; which are to be kept in mind by the couple. Therefore, the flaws of husband can be a reason for the revocation of Nikah by the wife only if the flaw is a permanent one and it will be certainly cause harm to the wife.</i></p>

Introduction

Allah (SWT) has made the religion of Islam in accordance with human nature, which is intended to protect people from harm and hardships, so that they do not bear sufferings for any reason. This is why the Sharia and Islamic rules are balanced, with neither excess nor exaggeration. For example, in the issue of separation between spouses, Islam does not concise its followers for only one marriage, like Hinduism does for whole life, willingly or unwillingly, for no reason, a person is bound to be in the same relationship, nor does it allow it to be a game and a pastime like Christians. Rather, Islam defines on the other hand, marriage as a long-term commitment. However, if for some reason the couples are unable to uphold their marriage or are fearful of violating each other's rights, the Islamic Shari'ah permits the termination of the marriage, so that spouses are not harmed. Therefore, , in Islamic Shari'ah, if the husband is given the conditional authority to grant divorce, then the wife is also given the authority to end the marriage relationship conditionally in the presence of certain defects in the husband, provided that in the presence of such defects, the purposes and benefits of the Islamic Sharia and marriage are dying. Therefore, contemporary scholars define such defect in these words:

“ العيب هو نقصان بدني أو عقلي في أحد الزوجين يجعل الحياة الزوجية غير مثمرة ”¹

(Defect means a physical or mental defect in one of the spouses that makes the marriage unproductive.)

As if the same defect will be effective for the separation between the spouses, in the presence of which there is a risk of death for the purposes of Sharia and marriage. In terms of faults in spouses, unbiased discussion on the faults of the husband is also necessary because in the case of faults found in the wife, the husband has the options of second wife and divorce. Whereas if there are such faults in the husband which the woman dislikes or because of which her life with her husband becomes untenable, then surely the purposes of the Sharia require the annulment of such a marriage so that the damage can be remedied from the wife. Because there is a well-known objective rule in Islamic Sharia that is:

“الضرر يزال”² (The damage will be removed).

Different viewpoints on the dissolution of marriage in the event that the husband has certain flaws can be found in fatwa books, thus it is only feasible to judge the correctness or incorrectness of these viewpoints in the context of sharia law and human welfare.

In the books of fatawa, there are different opinions regarding the dissolution of marriage in case of some defects in the husband, therefore, the assessment of the correctness or incorrectness of these opinions can only be possible in the light of the purposes of Sharia and human interests. Because after the marriage, the interests of each of the spouses are connected with the other, and in view of the risk of non-fulfillment or non-achievement

of the mutual benefits, the cases of annulment of a solemn contract such as marriage are also described in the Islamic Shari'ah.

1. The defect of insanity/madness in the husband and the requirements of the objectives of the Shari'ah : Madness is a disease in which a person suffering from it cannot distinguish between right/good and wrong/bad. That is why such a person can put himself to death. Therefore, an insane person is not bound by the Islamic law and is exempted from the rules of Shariah . Because the Shariah is based on wisdom and benefits, while an insane person does not have any interest in obtaining such benefits. Due to it, Majnun's marriage is thus impacted in this way as well. Scholars of the predecessors, however, have defined the defects capable of separation and annulment of marriage.ⁱⁱⁱ

But since there are countless defects which change their nature and status with the circumstances and time, the objectives of Sharia is the best measure to check the influence of it on the marriage. In which the jurists and Companions of Afta have also made a mistake. For example, in the books of fatawa, there are different opinions about the wife of an insane person: In the Fatawa of ashah ahlal Hadith (اصحابالحديث), the wife of Majnun has been given absolute authority to dissolve the marriage^{iv}. Similarly, in Fatawa Qasamiyyah one point of view is that, Majnun's wife has been given the right to demand absolute annulment of marriage^v.

While the other view mentioned in it is that, she can demand dissolution of marriage through the court^{vi}. However, in this case, Jamia Azhar's fatwa appears to be more in accordance with the objectives of Shari'ah, in which the Majnun's wife right to demand the annulment of the marriage was only conditionally accepted by the court only in certain circumstances, i.e. in case of necessity.^{vii} This is so because, as the Holy Qur'an indicates, Sharia's main objectives are the permanence and continuity of marriage.^{viii} Therefore, trying to justify the annulment of this contract from the existence of any minor harm is against the purposes of the Shari'ah. Due to this the early scholars consider the demand of the wife of an insane husband for the dissolution of marriage is to be against the spirit of Sharia^{ix}.

On the other hand if we consider, the husband has the option of divorce and remarriage, so far, the wife's insanity or madness does not cause him to suffer, therefore, the condition of necessity is not fulfilled in his favor in such a case. In the same way, even if the husband is insane, sometimes the woman is not in a state of necessity, therefore, in such situations, her demanding the annulment of the marriage is against the objectives of the Sharia. Therefore, in such a case, a woman should be determined and hopeful for which she will be rewarded by Allah Almighty. But if the woman has a strong apprehension about her rights due to her husband's insanity that they will be neglected, which will prove harmful for her to live with her husband. She can therefore apply to the court for a marital annulment in this situation, as indicated by Imam Muhammad in his saying, which is as follows:

“ لها الخيار دفع الضرر عنها ”^x

(A woman has the right to redress harm.)

In the same way, the state of insanity of husband plays a major role in proving the right of marriage's annulment for a woman, because sometimes the condition of madness is not of a nature that harms a woman. For example, minor insanity that occurs occasionally, which is eliminated by early treatment, does not entitle the woman to demand annulment of the marriage because it does not cause harm. Regarding this, **Qairwani** says that whether the madness is temporary or permanent, curable or incurable, the only condition for proof of a woman's right to demand dissolution of marriage is that it is painful and harmful for her. But if this harm can be removed by imprisoning the husband and the Nafaqah (Financial Support) of this woman is also being given equally, then she will not have the authority to demand the dissolution of the marriage^{xi}.

From this, it is known that in all cases of madness/insanity, it is important to keep in mind the objectives of Shariah; in the issue of the dissolution of marriage. And only in the case of fulfillment of the condition of necessity, the woman will have the right to demand the dissolution of the marriage. Because the continuity of the marriage relationship is also included in the objectives, which requires the cancellation of the woman's right to annul the marriage. Therefore, if primarily it is the goal to achieve the Shariah's objectives; Majnun's wife (wife of an insane person) will have the right to ask for the dissolution of the marriage. In this regard, the fatwa of Jamia Azhar are in accordance with the objectives of Sharia.

2. The issue (flaw) of husband's disappearance (شوبر کے مفقود ہونے کا عیب) and the requirements of the objectives of the Shari'ah :

- Missing (مفقود) means a person who is not known and no information about his condition is available. Its definition mentioned in kitaab al Hidayah:

“ اذا غاب الرجل فلم يعرف لموضع، ولا يعلم أحيوه أم ميت ”^{xii}

(When a person disappears and it is not known about him where he is, nor it is known whether he is alive or dead.)

- But among the Ahnaaf (أحناف), Mousali has defined it more comprehensively, according to him, missing means:

“ هو الذي غاب عن أهله ولم يدرك لميدراً أحيوه أم ميت، فلا يعلم مكانه، مضى عليه الكرم مانفوه معدوم بهذا الاعتبار ”^{xiii}.

(He is the one who is absent from his home and city and it is unknown whether he is alive or dead, and if there is no news of his presence even after a period of time has passed, then he is will be extinct.)

- While the definition attributed to Imam Malik is more reliable, according to him, **missing** means:

“هو الذي يبلغه سلطانو الاكتابسلطاناً فضلاً هلهو امامه في الارض فلا يدري أين هو وقد تلو موافق طلبه المسئلة عن فميو جد، فذا الكهو المفقود الذي يضرب له الامام في ما بلغ
 ١٤٧١٤

(He is the one to whom neither the king/ruler (imam) nor his message can reach, whose family and the imam do not know about him. And no one knows where he is, and they all get tired of searching him. So he is missing whose duration will be determined by the imam.)

Therefore, according to Malikia (مالكية), the determination of the waiting period for the wife of the missing person is more reasonable^{xv}. Because the Malikis differentiate between the **absent** and the **missing**, that's why they distinguish missing from the absent, not imposing the ruling of the missing on the absent. Therefore, their determination of the waiting period for the wife of the missing person seems to be compatible with the objectives of Sharia, and the wife of the missing is saved from harm in this case. While other jurisprudential legal systems (School of thoughts) do not discriminate between being absent and being missing^{xvi}. Therefore, the period stated by them is against the requirements of the objectives of the Shari'ah. While Maliki's write considering the absent and the missing separately:

"المفقود لا يسمى غائباً في اصطلاح الفقهاء" ^{xvii}

(In the terminology of the jurists, the missing person cannot be called absent.)

As a result, the absent person is the one who is not at home with his family and the news of his residence and survival has been cut off, or sometimes not cut off at all, but he is just away from home. It is found that while missing is specific, absence is common. As a result, there is a general and specific relationship between being absent and being missing, such that one cannot be applied to the other in absolute terms.

Fatwas related to the wife of the missing:

Various sayings can be found about the waiting period for the missing person's wife, in the books of Fatawa. According to the Fatawa of Ahlal Hadith (اهل الحديث), the wife can ask the dissolution of the marriage after waiting for a year, if the Qazi or ruler confirms that the government has not been able to find any information about the missing person after utilizing all available resources. If this confirmation has been made, there is no need to wait further^{xviii}. One of the Indian books of fatwas, Fatawa Qasmiyyah, states that the separation between the spouses can be done after waiting for a period of four years^{xix}.

Whereas according to Jamia Azhar's fatwa, no time period was determined or considered for the second marriage of the wife of missing. According to them, since marriage ends only with divorce or death, and Khula is also divorce with haq e mahr, therefore, according to them, the wife should not remarry until it is assured that the missing person has died.^{xx}

Review in the light of the Shari'ah's Objectives:

It is important to take into account the circumstances surrounding the disappearance of the missing person before deciding on the waiting period for the wife of a missing husband. Because there is a high possibility that giving a fatwa in this situation without taking into consideration the background would conflict with Sharia's goals. As a result, there are primarily two categories of Maqfuq-missing according to the jurists.

A case of missing person may be one in which there is a high probability of his/her survival with good health and safety, for example, he/she traveled for the purpose of trade or for the purpose of seeking knowledge or for the purpose of tourism; but could not returned to his/her family. If he does not come to his family, his ruling will be imprisonment because he has the choice to return to his family^{xxi}.

While the other general case of missing may be that in which there are more chances of his death, for example, he disappeared suddenly without informing his family and then the information about him were also cut off or maybe he disappeared in a war, or an accident occurred to a rider; in which some people survived and some got killed and the missing person was not found in any of them^{xxii}.

Likewise, it can also be divided in such a way that he was lost in the country of Muslims (دار الاسلام) or died in Darul Har (دار الحرب), or lost in a war between Muslims, or lost in a war between Muslims and non-muslims^{xxiii}. Therefore, in order to issue the fatwa in accordance with the objectives of Sharia, it is necessary to take into account the nature of the missing person before deciding the period for dissolution of marriage or remarriage for the wife of the missing person.

In the same way, the beginning of the waiting period for the remarriage of the missing wife also varies according to jurists' opinions as to when this waiting period will begin for the missing wife.

According to the Ahnaaf, regarding this is that the beginning of the period will not be valid, but the order of the judge will be valid, because the judge usually orders the separation of the spouses only after getting knowledge of the death of the missing person in any way or manner^{xxiv}.

There are different sayings related to this in Fiqh Maliki. According to one point of view, she will wait for four years after the order of the Qazi (judge)^{xxv}. Therefore, according to this opinion, after the order of the judge, the wife of the missing will start this period. In the same way, according to the second opinion, in Maliki jurisprudence, a wife of the missing- in a state of war will start waiting for a period of one year from the time of

her husband's disappearance^{xxvi}. Likewise, shawafi (شوافع) does not consider the beginning and end of the period for the wife of missing. Rather, they consider the judge's verdict as the final decision in this issue, and according to it the wife of a missing will be bound to follow the judge's order^{xxvii}. Whereas according to Hanabila, the wife of the missing will start the waiting period for her remarriage from the time of her husband's disappearance and not from the order of the judge^{xxviii}.

Therefore, in order to evaluate this problem in the light of the objectives of Sharia, the nature and the overall circumstances of the missing person will be measured, after which the methods utilized to search for it will be taken into account to determine their type. After that, the waiting period for his wife's remarriage will be decided; nevertheless, the Shari'ah's objectives argues that the waiting period for the missing person's wife is more in line with human objectives and goals if it begins after his disappearance has been proved.

Because each spouse's interests will be taken into account or considered when the wife of the missing person files for dissolution of marriage, i.e., the interests of the husband will be considered in addition to those of the wife too. As a result, if the missing person returns in the meantime, the goal of Sharia, which is to protect the offspring/generation, is placed at risk. This is because it is completely possible for the judge to declare the missing person as dead based on weak evidence while he is still alive, leading to his wife remarriage.

Therefore, the interests of each spouse should be taken into consideration before issuing the wife of the missing a dissolution of marriage, in order for the fatwa to be issued; should in line with the goals of Sharia. In this regard, Jamia Azhar's fatwa is the closest to the objectives of the Sharia, in which it is claimed that the marriage ends only with divorce or death^{xxix}. Likewise, the Hanafi viewpoint is therefore in accordance with the objectives of the Shari'ah in this matter, in which no time frame has been specified for the wife of the missing person to get remarried.^{xxx}

As the development of telecommunication, mass media and modern science, made it possible that if the missing person is alive, he can be traced, therefore the period for the remarriage of the wife of missing will not be considered. Because time duration, is not one of the reasons for dissolution of marriage, while in this matter, the judge will issue an order for dissolution of marriage in the light of the prevailing assumption that the missing person has died. As a result, according to all jurists, it is agreed that the wife of missing; for the second marriage will have to observe iddah of death.^{xxxi}

Because of this, the mufti must declare a fatwa while considering all the relevant facts, making sure that neither spouse suffers, or else the fatwa will be against the Shariah's objectives. Because of this, the jurists have allowed a wife whose husband does not provide her nafaqah (maintenance) to demand the dissolution of their marriage.^{xxxii} Therefore, the primary objective in this case will be to protect each of the spouses from harm. The fatwa that will meet the criteria of redressing the harm will be in accordance with the objectives of the Sharia.

Non-payment of the wife's financial rights/obligations

According to Islamic Shari'ah, the husband is responsible to provide the entire household financially. As Allah says:

”الرَّجَالُ قَوْمٌ عَلَى النِّسَاءِ بِمَا فَضَّلَ اللَّهُ بَعْضَهُمْ عَلَى بَعْضٍ بِمَا آتَفَقُوا مِنْ أَمْرِ اللَّهِ”^{xxxiii}

(Men are the protectors of women, as God gave some advantage over others, and because they spend their wealth)

Therefore, it is the husband's responsibility to provide for all essential necessities, non-spending has been identified by jurists as one of the husband's flaw/fault. In this situation, the wife has the right to ask for the dissolution of the marriage^{xxxiv}.

In the books of fatawa related to this matter, the scholars of hadeeth (اصحابالحديث) have also adopted the view that in case of non-payment of financial rights, the woman has the right to ask the court for the dissolution of marriage^{xxxv}. And In Fatawae Qasamiyyah, such a wife has also been given the right to demand the dissolution of marriage, whose husband, despite having the power to pay the rights such as nafaqah (Financial maintenance) etc., deliberately deprives his wife of it^{xxxvi}. While this issue has been addressed in the context of the objectives of Shariah, in the Jamia Azhar's fatwa, among the fatawa books, in which the justification of a woman's demand for dissolution of marriage has been described as conditional with harm/damage^{xxxvii}.

However, once the marriage bond has been formed, each spouse's interests have been established with one another, requiring the protection of it by both the spouses. As well as, Islamic Sharia has established the financial restrictions and limits regarding Infaq (spending money on one's family), because Islam creates balance in spending; as it forbids both extravagance and miserliness. Therefore, a woman should not have the authority to demand the dissolution of a marriage based solely on the non-provision of Nafaqah. Instead, this reason should be subject to the fulfillment of the condition of necessity.

Allah Almighty has said:

”وَإِنْ كَانَتْ فِي غُرْبَةٍ فَقَطِّرْهُ”^{xxxviii} “الْيَمِينَةَ”

(But if he is in hardship, then deferment until a time of ease)

Likewise, the wife should wait for her husband to become prosperous before asking a divorce or khula if the husband is unable to meet her basic necessities due to poverty. As after marriage the interests of each of the spouses are connected with one another, so each of the spouses should try not to harm the other on his behalf. Because of this, the Fatawa Qasmiyah stated that a woman's demand for dissolution of marriage; when her husband refused to change his residence was illegitimate^{xxxix}. Because in such a case, there is a risk of harm by obeying the wife, for which the wife has not been given the authority to demand the annulment of the marriage, and the basis for this is the purposeful rule that Allah has described as follows:

«لَا يُكَلِّفُ اللَّهُ نَفْسًا إِلَّا وُسْعَهَا»^{xl}

(Allah does not burden any soul beyond its capacity)

Therefore, the wife can only ask for the annulment of marriage; if it is absolutely necessary. If, however, both the husband's and the wife's harms are present, the major harm will be removed while the smaller harm will be tolerated, as it is stated in the famous Sharia's objective principle:

«الضرر الأشد يزال بالضرر الأخف»^{xli}

(Major harm will be avoided by tolerating minor harm)

Therefore, when the benefits of both are combined in this issue, the condition that is accepted will be the one in which more benefits may be achieved and retained. As a result, in this case, the fatwa of Qasmiyah regarding the illegitimacy of the wife's request for an annulment of the marriage due to a change of house is in line with the objectives of Shariah.

3. Flaws and fatwas related physical diseases of husband

It refers to all the diseases that affect a person other than sexual diseases, some of which have been considered by the early scholars to be capable of dissolution of marriage and separation between spouses. For example, insanity, leprosy and Vitiligo etc^{xlii}. Leprosy and vitiligo are actually referred to the disease of the flesh and its decay, which do not exist in the modern age. Additionally, Zuhri claims that the demand for dissolution of marriage is valid in case of incurable disease^{xliii}.

While it is stated in Fatawa Qasmiyah, one of the fatwa books, that the physical illness that results in the husband causing him extremely weak and vulnerable; enables his wife to demand that the marriage be terminated^{xliiv}. But this point of view is not in accordance with the objectives of Shariah, because there are many Shari'a objectives and purposes associated with marriage and the interests of the spouses, the protection of which cannot be put in danger due to a minor effort. For this reason, the jurists differ on the authority of the wife to demand the dissolution of the marriage due to illness in the husband^{xliiv}.

However, the jurists have recognized various diseases as sufficient grounds for dissolution of the marriage and used the title "Qiyas" (a rule in Islamic law) to conditions like insanity, leprosy, and vitiligo^{xlivi}. Likewise, in the present age there are many diseases due to which the Sharia's objectives allow the wife to demand the annulment of marriage. While it is a different matter that in some physical diseases, the objectives of the Shariah in favor of the wife are fulfilled in the level of necessity, in others, they are fulfilled in the level of requirement and in others; they are fulfilled in the level of approval. However, as many disorders cannot be described in writing, the evidence or non-evidence of the termination of the demand in favor of the wife can be explained by the harm caused to the wife. For example:

1. Due to the presence of these diseases, Vati (intercourse) and its pleasure are disturbed whether they are permanent diseases or defects in ethical values, morals and behaviors etc.
2. Diseases due to which the wife hates her husband and fears that she will be negligent in paying the rights of her husband due to human nature.
3. The disease, which the wife views as a source of shame for herself and could harm her morally and spiritually.
4. The disease in which there is a risk of being transferred to the wife means that the disease is contagious.
5. A disease that threatens to harm the wife, such as insanity, etc., in which the husband beats his wife.

Therefore, in all diseases, these are the causes that sometimes justify the demand for dissolution of marriage in favor of the wife. But such reasons do not absolutely prove the wife's right of dissolution, but the reason for the proof of annulment from them is that they are harmed, but if the wife does not feel harmed by her husband even in the presence of such diseases and she agrees to continue the marriage, then the right to demand the dissolution of the marriage is not applicable^{xliiv}.

Therefore, the wife does not get the right to demand the annulment of the marriage due to every single disease, because the essence of the marriage is its continuity, that is related to the objectives of Shariah of protecting and honoring the generation. Therefore, for its dissolution, the objectives of the Shari'ah must be fulfilled in the level of need or necessity. In this sense, this fatwa of Fatawa Qasmiyah is more compatible with the Sharia's objectives, in which the demand of a wife of the husband suffering from TB for dissolution of marriage has been declared illegitimate^{xlviii}.

Flaws related to sexually transmitted diseases

It refers to the diseases that are related to the male and female reproductive organs, in which diseases of the testicles are also described. Contemporary scholars refer to sexual diseases as diseases that occur during

intimacy and pleasure^{xlix}. While in the books of fatawa, sexual diseases refer to impotence and infertility in the reproductive capacity of the husband.

The jurists call the husband's impotence as Anin (عنين)^l. That is, the one whose penis is healthy, but he does not have the power to have sexual intercourse, but the jurists did not include (قلت امساک عنه) in the disease, nor does the wife have the right to get khula (خلع) or the right to annul it^{li}, so she cannot immediately get khula from her husband; if he does not have the power to have sexual intercourse^{lii}. Likewise, Fatwae Qasamiyyah, has given a fatwa on the illegitimacy of a woman's immediate demand for khula^{liii}.

Because the wife demands khula, or the dissolution of the marriage, when there is a condition in which she gets harm or danger. However, the impotence of husband does not cause any such harm to the wife that the strongest contract of marriage to be annulled and the protection of the husband's interests should be put at risk. Therefore, the jurists agreed that the husband will be given a one-year grace period to treat the woman's accusation. Therefore, during this time, if the husband recovers from treatment, her right to demand divorce or annulment will be revoked, but if he cannot recover during this time and the woman does not agree to live with her husband so, she has the right to demand the dissolution of the marriage^{liv}, so that the harm can be alleviated. The reason for this respite is that sometimes the inability to have sexual intercourse is temporary, which cannot be considered as a disease, therefore, it is a presumptive argument for the annulment of marriage, due to which the annulment of a great contract like marriage is not possible. But if the indication of this disease becomes definite on the dissolution of marriage, for example, in the present age, the modern forms of examinations in the medical field; it is possible to clear the situation that this disease is permanently present in the husband, and even after spending a period of one year, modern medicine proves the permanent presence of this disease, in such a case, his wife has the right to demand dissolution of marriage through the court^{lv}.

From this, it is known that there are several forms of this disease depending on the severity of the disease; therefore, the same order cannot be imposed on all these cases. Thus, among the fatawa books in this issue, the fatwa of Jamia Azhar seems to be compatible with the objectives of Shariah, in which a very comprehensive, rather a permanent principle, has been described regarding the impotent husband and the various forms of this disease.

“منعجز عنا لامساك المعروف وجعلها لتسر يحبا لاحسان”^{lvi}

(Whoever is unable to keep the wife in a known manner, it is obligatory on him to leave her away with kindness/gentleness.)

Therefore, every case of this disease in which the husband knows that he cannot fulfill the sexual needs of his wife and it will cause harm to his wife, then it is necessary for him to leave her with kindness, so that the benefits of each of the spouses can be protected.

Loss of the husband's ability of reproduction

Either husband or wife can be deprived of the ability of reproduction, as Allah Almighty has said:

”لِلّٰهِ مُلْكُ السَّمٰوٰتِ وَالْاَرْضِ ط يَخْلُقُ مَا يَشَآءُ ط يَهَبُ لِمَنْ يَّشَآءُ اِنَاثًا وَّ يَهَبُ لِمَنْ يَّشَآءُ الذَّكَوٰرَ اَوْ يُزَوِّجُهُمْ ذُكْرَانًا وَّ اِنَاثًا جُوِّعَلُ مَنْ يَّشَآءُ“^{lvii}

(To Allah belongs the dominion of the heavens and the earth. He creates whatever He wills. He grants daughters to whomever He wills, and He grants sons to whomever He wills. Or He combines them together, males and females; and He renders whomever He wills infertile.)

Therefore, the Holy Qur'an has declared a husband and wife who are deprived of reproductive ability to be infertile that is why the jurists call such a person infertile (عقيم). And infertile is one who is childless after a year or more of marriage.^{lviii}

Among the fatwa books, in the fatwa of Jamia Azhar, a fatwa has been given on the invalidity of the demand for divorce (khula) or dissolution of marriage to the wife of an infertile husband^{lix}. Likewise, the Lajna Daimah (لجنة دائمة) of Saudi Arabia has also declared this disease as insufficient for the annulment of marriage, but according to them, morally, the husband should inform the woman prior marriage; if he knows about this disease before the marriage, so that she does not get harm.^{lx}

However, there are various views within Islamic law regarding what constitutes sufficient evidence to annul a marriage due to a disease, as well as what does not. One viewpoint holds that infertility is a flaw that can lead to divorce since it harms the spouses^{lxi}. While according to the second opinion, infertility is not a defect that can cause separation between spouses^{lxii}. According to the third opinion, if the wife has this disease, the husband cannot dissolve the marriage; however, if the husband has it, the wife has the right to request that the marriage be terminated.^{lxiii}

While there are different forms of infertility, it often happens that a couple does not have children in their early years of marriage, but Allah Almighty blesses them with children in their old age. Thus, sometimes the child is born after waiting for many years while sometimes the infertility is chronic in nature, in which there is a risk of harming the woman. However, modern medicine has also found a solution to this issue, making it easier than ever to use it to determine if the infertility is temporary or permanent.

Therefore, if the husband has chronic infertility and a group of qualified doctors confirms that, then in this situation, the validity or invalidity of the claim for dissolution of marriage depends on the circumstances and

sentiments of the wife. The objectives of Sharia therefore dictate that the demand for dissolution of marriage becomes invalid if the wife accepts to live with her husband in such a situation. However, if the woman suffers harm, she has the right to request that the marriage be dissolved because, in such circumstance, the marital goals of love and mercy would not have been fulfilled^{ixiv}.

Similarly, the wife typically suffers more harm from the husband's infertility because she has fewer opportunities to remarry in the subcontinent. Although the husband has the option of remarrying if the wife is infertile, in this case, the husband is less harmed by the wife's disease. But despite this, a fatwa may however be issued in light of the relevant facts while taking the individual's situation into account. Because the ability to demand dissolution of marriage in cases of infertility has been completely denied in some books of fatwas related to this matter, they are not in accordance with the objectives of Shariah.

Conclusion

One of the Sharia's requirements for marriage is permanence and continuity, whereas one of marriage's objectives is to build a relationship of love, affection, and mercy between the spouses so that the next generation's upbringing can be in a better and more joyful environment. While lack of trust, love and mercy, between spouses; affects the next generation. Therefore, the Shari'ah's objectives request for the elimination of spouse differences so that the marriage relationship can continue. However, if this is not the case and the husband and wife's differences persist, then in this situation, the separation of the couple is preferable so that these differences do not negatively affect the next generation. Additionally, the Sharia's goals state that neither spouse should do harm to the other, with the exception of the woman, who would suffer significantly more harm as a result of the husband's flaws. It is because the husband has the right to remarry due to the flaws in the wife, but the wife cannot marry twice at the same time. Therefore, if the wife is harmed due to the defects found in the husband and those defects are permanent, then if the wife is willing to live with the husband despite such defects, then it is her right to live with him. And if she does not like him, then the objectives of Sharia require that they should be separated so that the wife can be protected from harm.

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